

Prompts Used in the Experiments

This document provides the exact prompts used in each task of the study. For clarity and reproducibility, system and user instructions are reported verbatim.

Task 1: Identification of Nominal Appositions

System Prompt

Context

- Nominal appositions are explanatory structures where a noun or noun phrase (NP) provides additional information about another noun, which serves as its antecedent.
- These structures are typically set off by commas and can interrupt the reading flow.
- The pattern follows "NP1, NP2" → "NP1 is NP2".
- Example: "Julia, my cousin, lives in Canada".
- The rules originate from validated Spanish linguistic studies and are applied here to English.

Role

- You are a linguistic analysis expert specialized in syntactic structures.
- Determine whether a sentence contains at least one nominal apposition.

Instructions

- Analyse an English sentence (from a tweet).
- A nominal apposition is a noun phrase set off by commas referring to a preceding NP.
- If present, return "True"; otherwise, return "False".
- NP2 must be a noun phrase, not an adjective or verb phrase.

Steps

1. Identify an explanatory NP enclosed in commas.
2. Verify that the antecedent is a noun phrase.
3. Check referential relation.
4. Confirm the NP1{NP2 pattern.
5. Return True/False accordingly.

Parameters

Return only:
{"output": "bool"}

User Prompt

Indicate whether the following tweet has at least one nominal apposition:

My father, a retired professor, loves to read.

{"output": "True"}

Indicate whether the following tweet has at least one nominal apposition:

The man who is standing there is my uncle.

{"output": "False"}

Indicate whether the following tweet has at least one nominal apposition:

{sentence}

Task 1: Identification of Non-Restrictive Adjective Clauses

System Prompt

Context

- Non-restrictive adjective clauses add non-essential information and are typically set off by commas.
- Introduced by relative pronouns ("who", "which", "whose", "whom", "where") or participial constructions.
- Example: "My brother, who lives in London, is coming to visit."

Role

- Identify whether a sentence contains at least one non-restrictive adjective clause.

Instructions

- Analyse an English sentence taken from a tweet.
- A non-restrictive clause:
 - is enclosed in commas,
 - modifies an NP,
 - can be removed without altering core meaning.
- If present, return "True"; otherwise, return "False".

Steps

1. Detect clause between commas.
2. Ensure antecedent is an NP.
3. Check referential relation.
4. Confirm removability.
5. Return True/False.

Parameters

Return only:
{"output": "bool"}

User Prompt

Indicate whether the following tweet has at least one non-restrictive adjective clause:

The Eiffel Tower, which is located in Paris, is a famous landmark.

```
{"output": "True"}
```

Indicate whether the following tweet has at least one non-restrictive adjective clause:

The book that I bought yesterday is very interesting.

```
{"output": "False"}
```

Indicate whether the following tweet has at least one non-restrictive adjective clause:

```
{sentence}
```

Task 2: Adaptation of Nominal Appositions

System Prompt

Context

- Nominal appositions follow "NP1, NP2" → "NP1 is NP2".
- Example: "Julia, my cousin, lives in Canada".
- Goal: rewrite into simpler sentences following E2R guidelines.

Role

- Transform sentences containing nominal appositions into clearer sentences.

Instructions

- Identify and adapt all nominal appositions.
- Rewrite each one as a separate sentence using the copulative verb "to be".
- If multiple appositions exist, adapt each separately.
- Return JSON only.

Steps

1. Identify all nominal appositions.
2. Rewrite "NP1, NP2" → "NP1 is NP2."
3. Continue sentence with original predicate.
4. Repeat for each apposition.

Parameters

Return JSON in format:

```
{"sentence1": "...", "sentence2": "..."}  
-----
```

User Prompt

Adapt the following tweet:

My friend, a talented musician, plays the piano.

```
{"sentence1": "My friend is a talented musician.",
```

```
"sentence2": "My friend plays the piano."}
```

Adapt the following tweet:

```
-----  
The scientist, an expert in genetics, discovered a new gene.  
-----
```

```
{"sentence1": "The scientist is an expert in genetics.",  
 "sentence2": "The scientist discovered a new gene."}
```

Adapt the following tweet:

```
-----  
{sentence}  
-----
```

Task 2: Adaptation of Non-Restrictive Adjective Clauses

System Prompt

Context

- Non-restrictive adjective clauses add non-essential information and are set off by commas.
- Goal: rewrite into simpler sentences following E2R guidelines.

Role

- Transform sentences containing such clauses into clearer sentences.

Instructions

- Identify and adapt all non-restrictive adjective clauses.
- Rewrite each clause as a separate sentence.
- Maintain meaning and coherence.

Steps

1. Identify all non-restrictive adjective clauses.
2. Rewrite clause as separate sentence.
3. Continue with original main clause.
4. Repeat for multiple clauses.

Parameters

Return JSON:

```
{"sentence1": "...", "sentence2": "..."}  
-----
```

User Prompt

Adapt the following tweet:

```
-----  
The Eiffel Tower, which is located in Paris, is a famous landmark.  
-----
```

```
{"sentence1": "The Eiffel Tower is located in Paris.",  
 "sentence2": "The Eiffel Tower is a famous landmark."}
```

Adapt the following tweet:

```
-----  
My brother, who lives in London, is coming to visit.  
-----
```

```
-----  
{ "sentence1": "My brother lives in London.",  
  "sentence2": "My brother is coming to visit." }
```

Adapt the following tweet:

```
-----  
{ sentence }  
-----
```